

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Report

CZECH REPUBLIC

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

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Report

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Abstract

This report has been prepared as a part of the Horizon 2020 FUME project – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649) and its deliverable “D.6.3. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries”. It aims to analyse the migration profile of Czechia and to assess the country’s migration potential in order to provide material for the fine-tuning of the FUME migration projection model. Some of the variables the report takes into account are gender, age, country of origin and destination countries. The report is a first step in the analytical exercise which aims to determine migration movement potential both from and to the Czech Republic.

For Czech Republic, analogously to other Visegrad Group states, international migration is a phenomenon that over the last few years became substantially important politically, demographically and economically. The development of the migration policy has been taking place in the country since the 1990s. While the Czech economy has been experiencing increasing demand for foreign labour, the mainstream public narrative concerning immigrants (and asylum seekers in particular) and, consequently, shaping migration policy agenda, has been, especially recently, predominantly a securitarian one.

Some of the key moments concerning international migrations in the country’s recent history are the accession of Czechia to the European Union in 2004 and entering the Schengen Area three years later. The largest group of immigrants in the country is the group of Ukrainian citizens. Undoubtedly, the Russian annexation of Crimea and a military attack on Eastern Ukraine which subsequently led to the protracted armed conflict, has enhanced the inflow of Ukrainian migrants to the country and affected the structure of residence permits held by the nationals of this country, as we point out further in this analysis.

This report aims to briefly present the historical background for migration movements in the Czech Republic, in order to provide a better understanding of current challenges Czech society faces with regard to increased migration movements in general and immigration in particular. The authors of this report provide a general outline of the demography of migrant groups currently residing in Czechia. A separate part of this paper is focusing on the issue of the Czech diaspora globally. Apart from those, the authors of the report sketch a general analysis of migration policies introduced in Czechia. Finally, local data gathered from the Czech sources are juxtaposed with Guy Abel’s calculations and, based on those, a quantitative analysis of migration movements to and from the country is conducted.

1. Introduction

The political history of today's Czechia (or Czech Republic - authors of this report decided to use both names interchangeably) as an independent state began on the 1st of January 1993, with the dissolution of Czechoslovakia and establishment of the Czech Republic and the Slovak Republic. The analysis conducted for the purposes of this report focuses therefore mostly on the period of the last 30 years. It is nevertheless necessary to take account of the history of migration movements in the country and the region before the First World War, during the interwar period and after the Second World War.

The historical migrations from Czechia fit into the wider context of migratory movements from the Central-European region in the 19th and 20th centuries. It is estimated that between 1800 and 1925, more than 48 million people left Europe in search of a new life in Americas (especially in the USA, Canada, Argentina and Brazil) and Australia. Initially, the key sending countries were the United Kingdom, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Spain and Sweden. Soon after the initial period of the 19th century European emigration, also other European nations (including Czechs - as subjects of the Austro-Hungarian empire) started to contribute to the global migratory movements more actively. It is estimated that between 1850 and 1914, approximately 1.5 million ethnic Czechs, most of them agricultural and industrial workers, emigrated primarily to the United States of America, but also to Argentina, Austria, Brazil, Hungary, Russia, and countries of the former Yugoslavia in search of economic opportunities (Drbohlav and Janurová 2019).

The First World War significantly halted the Czech emigrations. After the 1918 the restrictions on immigration from Czechoslovakia had been introduced by the US, the most important emigration destination for Czechs at the time. This, however, did not prevent the migration movement entirely. The emigration of ethnic Czechs had peaked in the early 1920s, however afterwards the phenomenon continued until the end of the 1930s. It is also worth mentioning that following the World War I, 40 000 Czechs returned to their country of birth from the United States, whereas about 100 000 returned from Austria. However, as this migration inflow has been smaller than the migration outflows at the time consequently the country's population decreased during the interwar period. It is also worth remembering that ethnic Germans constituted almost one third of the Czechoslovak population of the interwar period (Drbohlav and Janurová 2019). Apart from the international migration movements, also a significant internal migrational mobility had been witnessed in the country. Over the interwar period more Czechs migrated to Slovakia (e.g. in 1930 over 121 thousand - primarily a reflection of the filling of jobs in the new state and public service by Czech workers) than Slovaks migrated to Czechia (in 1930 over 44 thousand). After 1945, during the Communist period, the dynamics of this movement changed and more Slovaks came to Czechia than Czechs arrived in Slovakia. This was partially linked with the expulsion of the German population from the Sudetenland and the ethnic Czechs and Slovaks moving into the region (Bahna 2011: 29).

After the Second World War Czechoslovakia had been incorporated into the Soviet sphere of influence and thus the external migration from and into the country was strongly limited. The two political events which had caused significant outflow of citizens from Czechoslovakia (both Czechs and Slovaks) were the communist coup in 1948 and the military intervention and subsequent occupation of Czechoslovakia by the Soviet bloc troops in 1968. According to some sources, during the most intensive emigration period of 1948 - 1950 over 23 thousand citizens fled the country. During, the second of the aforementioned events that is the occupation of Czechoslovakia by Warsaw Pact troops (from August 1968 till the end of 1969) over 100 thousand citizens fled the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic (Ratica 2006 quoted in Bahna 2011: 58). They most frequently emigrated to Switzerland, Canada, Austria and Germany. According to the experts, in the second episode of dynamic outflow of people from the country, there were many more Czechs than Slovaks amongst those fleeing. This was linked to the more intense participation of Czechs in the events of the Prague Spring, as well as better access to information and social networks necessary to leave the country.

It is estimated that between 1948 and 1989 up to a half a million people left Czechoslovakia (Jungwirth et al 2019: 18). A great share of them were high-skilled migrants who easily adapted to the life in their new countries of residence, gradually losing both their connection to the country of origin and sometimes Czechoslovak citizenship. Thus, these people might fall outside of the diaspora statistics we consider for the purposes of this report. One of the emblematic figures who participated in this process has been a Czech writer Milan Kundera, who went into exile in 1975 and in 1979 lost Czechoslovak citizenship. He was granted Czech citizenship only in 2019.

While after the Velvet Revolution over 100 thousand Slovaks decided to return to Slovakia the Czech community in Slovakia lost only slightly over 10 thousand members in the first decade following the establishment of the independent Slovak and Czech Republics (Bahna 2011: 69).

The awareness of the aforementioned facts from the Czech (as well as shared Czechoslovak) migration history is crucial to understand not only the diasporic connections, but also some of the most recent migration movements analysed below.

Picture: Ryan Lum/Unsplash.com

2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources

This report has been prepared using desk research methodology. The authors utilised secondary data analysis for its purposes. The materials concerning migrational inflows and outflows that are the substantial part of this analysis had been collected between January and May 2021. The main sources of information for this assessment were various public statistical databases, both local and international. The authors analysed data published among others by: the Czech Statistical Office, Eurostat, Ministry of the Interior of the Czech Republic, Czech Police. Various other academic studies were also taken into account. Moreover, the final part of the report refers to the estimations on the immigrant flows proposed by Abel & Cohen in 2019.

3. Migration policy development

Development of the Czech migration policy after the fall of communism

With the regime change in 1989 and the Velvet Revolution, the Czech Republic experienced a major shift in international migrations. The country became increasingly attractive for various categories of immigrants and began to shape its policy in this area. Although the migration policy was not a primary concern for the government of the Czech Republic in the early 90s (Stojarová 2019: 100), that decade brought a major change in this domain. This issue has been pointed out also by Horáková:

The fundamental break in the main trends in international migration as it affects the Czech Republic has occurred since 1990. The opening of the borders in January 1990 and the new freedom of movement resulted in higher levels of migration movements. Indeed, the underlying principles governing the situation of migrants coming to and leaving the Czech Republic were overturned (Horáková 2000: 7).

While explaining the development of migration policy in Czechia it is useful to refer to the framework introduced by Kušniráková and Čížinský (quoted in Stojarová 2019: 106), where the relevant policies are analysed with regard to the following two oppositions: liberal versus restrictive policies and the preference for integration versus circular migration. The former concerns the very possibilities of entering the country for the migrants, in other words, the question of whether the state system is open to receiving foreigners. The latter, on the other hand, refers to the settlement process. The issue in question here is if actions of state actors' aim at facilitating the longer or permanent stay of migrants or at maintaining the temporary character of migration.

Under the introduced framework, Stojarová describes newly established migration and integration policies of Czechia in the 90s as liberal, however leaning towards circular migration. The years between 1990 and 1996 are seen as the beginning of the process of institutionalization of Czech migration policy. The adoption of 'Act no. 123/1992 Coll. of 4 March 1992 on Foreigners' Stay and Residence in the Czech and Slovak Federal Republic' has been a major event of the period:

The first migration law valid for both parts of the Czech and Slovak federation was adopted in 1992 [...]. It basically enabled anyone to settle in the country without limiting any of his/her activities, and allowed an applicant to apply for both long-term and permanent visas directly in the country (Stojarová 2019: 100).

The later period of 1996-1999 had been marked with three significant developments. The first of these was the young Republic repealing non-visa agreements with post-Soviet countries - the major immigration countries for the Czech Republic at the time. The second was adoption of the new law on migration in 1999, more restrictive than the one previously applied, which resulted in the decrease in the number of immigrants residing in the Czech Republic (Stojarová 2019: 107). The third of the mentioned events was the change in the law on asylum, in such a way that it corresponded with the European Union regulations (Stojarová 2019: 101). Both documents leaned towards the policy aiming at foreigners' long-term integration.

Then, the five-year period before the EU accession in 2004 is referred to as the 'consolidating era', when the state has been introducing further changes in order to guarantee the convergence of its local law with international law. Stojarová points out also the 'mobilization of civil society' in that period (Stojarová 2019: 100). After the accession, the similar direction of the policy development has been in place for the next three years until a major policy shift occurred in 2008 when the so-called 'neo-restrictive period' commenced and more restrictive policies supported by security-related arguments started to be gradually institutionalized (Stojarová 2019: 101). That year the competencies in the field of migration were transferred from the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs to the Ministry of Interior (hereafter: MI), which, consequently, in the further years pushed the development of Czech migration policy towards the restrictive pole (Stojarová 2019: 107).

The recent development of migration policy context in Czechia

The decade of 2010s did not bring a substantial shift in agenda shaping migration policy of the country. On the contrary, the Czech government, similarly to the governments of other countries in the region, has been increasingly adopting a right-wing narrative and attitude towards international migrations, speaking against refugee admission during the so-called 'migration crisis' in 2015, and focusing its migration policy on qualified migration with greater prospects of long-term integration.

Currently, as already mentioned, the state's migration and integration policy, its asylum-related agenda and governance of the inflow and outflow of migrants from the Czech Republic have been shaped by the Ministry of Interior. The MI is supported in its work by other ministries, the Ombudsman and the Committee for the Rights of Foreigners, which includes the representatives of the civil society (Jungwirth et al 2019: 19). Then, the principal documents concerning the issue of international migration in the Czech Republic are listed by Jungwirth and colleagues as follows:

The crucial national law concerning migration is the Foreigners Act (Act No. 326/1999) on the Residence of Foreign Nationals in the Territory of the Czech Republic. [...] [E]mphasis has been given to the elaboration of non-legislative executive policy, primarily by the Interior Ministry. Building upon six Migration Policy Principles (MI 2018c), the key relevant strategic documents are the Strategy of Czech Migration Policy (MI 2015) and the regularly updated Policy of Foreigner Integration (MI 2018b), with inputs from stakeholders including civil society (2019: 19).

During the migration crisis in 2015 (sometimes referred to also as the refugee crisis or, as we suggest to call it instead: the crisis of European solidarity) the representatives of the rightist governments of Czechia, Poland and Hungary have repeatedly been expressing Islamophobic and civilisationist views (Brubaker 2017, Bayrakli and Hafez 2017), while raising security arguments against accepting the asylum seekers fleeing from the conflict zones. This position has been officially acknowledged in a joint statement of governments of Visegrad Group countries:

Preserving the voluntary nature of EU solidarity measures – so that each Member State may build on its experience, best practices and available resources; principles agreed at the highest political level, including in European Council conclusions must be respected; any proposal leading to introduction of mandatory and permanent quota for solidarity measures would be unacceptable (Government of the Czech Republic 2015).

Eventually, the Central-European states almost uniformly rejected the quota system proposed by the European Union:

The quota mechanism introduced in the summer of 2015 in the wake of a proposal by the Commission then presided over by Jean-Claude Juncker, did not lead to the desired effect since it was not respected by certain Member States, like Hungary and Poland, or was only slightly respected by others such as Austria and the Czech Republic (Bloj & Buzmaniuk 2020).

In a 2016 interview for the 'Expres.cz' the PM of Czechia, Andrej Babis, said: "After what has been happening in Europe, I say clearly that I don't want even a single refugee in the Czech Republic, not even temporarily" (Reuters 2016). According to the information published in 2018 in 'Infomigrants.com', the Czech Republic accepted 12 migrants out of 2000 that were meant to be relocated to the country by that time (Dambach 2018). That general standpoint and the decisions taken by the Central-European countries' governments met with outrage from the international public opinion. The critique came both from within Czechia, Hungary and Poland, mostly from the third-sector organizations (for example, in Czechia, from an umbrella-organization for migration-related NGOs: 'Consortium of Migrants Assisting Organizations in the Czech Republic <2015a>'), as well as from outside the region, from other, European countries engulfed in the crisis. In 2020 the European Court of Justice found this approach of Czechia, Hungary and Poland breaching European law. It has been acknowledged in the ruling from the 2nd of April 2020:

First, the Court concluded that there had been an infringement, by the three Member States concerned, of a decision adopted by the Council with a view to the relocation, on a mandatory basis, from Greece and Italy of 120 000 applicants for international protection to the other Member States of the European Union. Secondly, the Court found that Poland and the Czech Republic had also failed to fulfil their obligations under an earlier decision that the Council had adopted with a view to the relocation, on a voluntary basis, from Greece and Italy of 40 000 applicants for international protection to the other Member States of the European Union (p. 1).

In December 2018, during the United Nations assembly, the Czech Republic voted against the introduction of the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration (together with the USA, Israel, Poland and Hungary) (Echo24.cz, 2021) and recently, hand in hand with Poland and Hungary, the country has been opposing the introduction of the European Union's new Pact on Migration and Asylum (Euronews 2020). Babis, similarly to the other prominent, middle-European right-wing politicians in the recent year, have been playing securitisation card, raising concerns about the 'illegal migration', human trafficking business, and security of external borders of the European Union (Agence France Presse 2020, Wintour 2018).

Nevertheless, the Czech Republic, similarly to the other countries of the region, experiences the outcomes of the demographic crisis and an increased demand for the labour force is being observed in the country (Chwiej 2017: 7-13). These factors, together with a significant growth of the number of Ukrainian residents in the Central European region, resulted in the new reality, where the Czech Republic, having transitioned to a country of transit after 1989, started to witness substantially increasing numbers of immigrants in the first decade of the 21st century (Janská at al. 2014: 681). However, it needs to be noted that the very net migration rates for Czech Republic have been reaching values above 0 since the late 1980s (Net migration - Czech Republic 2019). Currently Czechia can be described as a new immigration destination (Winders 2014), due to the increase of substantial significance of the immigration phenomenon in a local, social and economic context:

Today, it is by far the most attractive destination for migrants in post-communist Central and Eastern Europe. [...] the refugee crisis aside, the era since 2013 has witnessed a major demand for foreign labor as economic stability and resumed prosperity resulted in many new migrants entering the country. Between 2016 and 2017, the country saw an increase of 90,000 workers, as measured through employee registrations (Drbohlav & Janurová 2019).

The new Asylum Law introduced in 2015 liberalised the access of asylum seekers to the Czech labour market. At the same time, the competences of the Ministry of Interior have been extended and it has been turned into an 'absolute arbiter' in asylum cases (Stojarová 2019: 107-108).

Then, on July 2015 the new Strategy on Migration Policy of the Czech Republic (original title in Czech: Strategie migrační politiky České republiky) (MI 2015 a) has been accepted by the parliament. The very fact of the establishment of the new Strategy has been approved of by the third-sector organisations, but its content, on the other hand, sparked criticism (Consortium of Migrants Assisting Organizations in the Czech Republic 2015 b). It has been pointed out that the general view on international migrations expressed in the document had been a securitarian one, as the need to ensure national safety had been made the first of seven key principles of the strategy (MI 2015 a: 2). This, particular element of the strategy had been acknowledged as the one that cross-cuts the others (MI 2015 b). Moreover, the NGOs highlighted that migrations have been pictured in the Strategy as a negative phenomenon that potentially poses numerous threats to the host society. It had been underlined that the authors of the document, apart from the securitarian ones, adopted economic lenses, thus overlooking the wider, humanitarian perspective (Consortium of Migrants Assisting Organizations in the Czech Republic 2015 b).

Two years later, in 2017, the new amendments to the Czech Aliens Act were introduced (in Czech: Novela Zákona o pobytu cizinců na území České republiky <Zákon č. 326/1999 Sb.>) (Amendment to Czech... 2017). The document, signed by president Milos Zeman in July 2017, moved the Czech migration policy further towards the restrictive pole. The changes introduced included tightening of the rules applying to employment of foreigners' in Czechia and substantial extension of powers held by the Ministry of Interior (Czech Republic: Stricter rules... 2017). At the same time, the amendments enabled the foreigners working in the Czech Republic to stay in the country for at least half a year, without a need to apply for extension of their three-months visas. Another group that did benefit from the changes were foreigners conducting business activities related to investment, who had been allowed to stay in the country for up to two years.

The consecutive amendments signed in 2019, most importantly, introduced a new legal instrument called 'the employee card'. This new type of long-term residence permit has been introduced in order to limit 'predatory practices' of employment intermediaries (Beneš 2019), by disallowing the foreign workers to change their employers during the initial six months of the stay in Czechia (Czech parliament approves... 2019). Among other substantial changes were those introduced with regard to economic migration. For example, governmental programmes for labour migrants from eastern-European and Asian states have been extended to nationals' of countries previously not included.

Since the beginning of 2021, the obligatory, paid adaptation-integration courses for foreigners arriving in the Czech Republic have been introduced. The contents of the course include 'the rights and obligations connected to their stay in the territory of the Czech Republic, with the fundamental values of the Czech Republic, and with the country's everyday life, culture and customs.' (Czech Republic: Integration and... 2021).

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4. Entry and legalisation of employment and residence in the Czech Republic

Entry to the Czech Republic

The conditions of entry on the territory of Czech Republic are subject to international regulations concerning the Schengen Area. As Czechia is a Schengen State, the country applies Schengen common visa policy 'for transit through or intended stays on the territory of Schengen States of no more than 90 days in any 180 days period and for transit through the international transit areas of airports of the Schengen States' (European Commission 2021). The country does not border with any non-Schengen State. Therefore, as the Schengen Area is a zone of free international movement, there are no border-checks at the frontiers. The only cross-border movement in and out of the Schengen Area that Czechia is concerned with directly is the movement through the countries' airports.

Legalisation of residence in the Czech Republic for the EU nationals

The conditions of legalization of residence and employment in the Czech Republic differ between those relevant to the EU nationals and those aimed at the third country nationals. Since May 2004 every EU national may travel to Czech Republic or reside in the country without applying for residence permit nor visa (Embassy of the Czech republic in the Hague 2018), however, according to MI, in case their stay exceeds the period of 30 days they are expected to report it in an appropriate police station (MI 2017).

Those EU citizens who intend to stay in Czech Republic for a period longer than three months may apply for a certificate of temporary residence permit for the EU citizens or members of their family. This kind of permit is issued at the request of the EU national and filing such application is not an obligation, as receiving a residence permit is not a condition of stay in Czechia for the EU citizens:

If you intend to stay in the CR for longer than 3 months, you are entitled, but in no way obliged, to apply for a certificate of temporary residence in the CR. This certificate can simplify your stay in the CR in many ways – for instance, when buying property, opening building savings or arranging pension insurance; it can also help in proving the length of residence in the CR for the purpose of a future application for permanent residence (MI 2011: 6).

The family members of the EU nationals, as understood by MI (MI 2016), who are not EU-citizens themselves are not required to apply for visa if they plan to stay in Czech Republic up to three months - they are entitled to stay in the country legally on the basis of residence permit issued by other EU country and valid travel document they hold. However, if they plan to stay in the Czech Republic for a longer period then they must apply for a temporary residence permit issued by Czech authorities on a relevant basis (MI 2017). Such may be also the very fact of being the family member of the EU national residing legally in Czech Republic (MI 2019a).

The certificates of temporary residence permit are issued by the Ministry of Interior of the Czech Republic (MI) and since the 31st of December 2019 all newly issued documents are valid for a period of two years. Interestingly, the Czech Republic does not issue the temporary residence permits to the third country nationals, thus this statutory instrument is only available to the EU citizens and their families. Presumably, that can be identified as one of the reasons why in the Czech statistics the long-term immigrants outnumber those residing in the country on a basis of the short-term residence permits, in contrast to, for example, neighbouring Poland.

Legalisation of residence in the Czech Republic for the third country nationals

Third country nationals (understood as: 'citizens of countries neither members of the EU, nor citizens of Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland, nor their family members.' <MI 2019>) are entitled to reside in the territory of Czech Republic under certain conditions. They are obliged to register the place of their residence in the 'Residence Administration Unit of Alien Police Department within Regional Police Directorate' within three days from their arrival in the country (Policie Ceske republiky 2020). Moreover, they are expected to be able to present the proof of obtaining a travel health insurance covering all the period of their stay in Czechia and they must report all changes concerning the data included in their travel documents and in the documents that entitle them to stay on the territory of the Czech Republic.

There are a few, differing legal pathways to obtaining a legal residence permit in Czechia for third country nationals. Apart from those foreigners who hold Schengen visas entitling them to enter and reside within the Area, there are also nationals of such countries, which are exempt from Schengen visa-regulations, e.g. Canada, Serbia, Hong Kong or Ukraine. Since 2017, Ukrainian nationals are entitled to reside in the Schengen Area for 90 days out of every 180 without applying for visa (ETIAS 2021 a), which, as we will point further, is an important fact in context of migratory inflow to Czechia.

It is desirable to point, that regulations concerning the visa-free Schengen Area entry are going to change for third country nationals in late 2022, when European Travel Information and Authorization System (ETIAS) will be put in place. Since then the nationals of all the countries that are currently exempt from visa requirements who would want to enter one of the ETIAS countries (Czechia among them) and then travel freely within the area the ETIAS will be obliged to apply for so-called: 'European visa waiver' document. The aim of establishing the ETIAS system, which in its principles and objectives is going to be similar to the United States' ESTA, is to increase the security of the member states. That is going to be giving the border forces the tools for screening the foreigners arriving in the area by cross-checking the information on the arriving in various databases (ETIAS 2021 b).

Those third country nationals who do not hold Schengen visa (short-term visas or long-term visas for periods exceeding 90 days) nor stay in the Area on a basis of visa-exemption are obliged to apply for the residence permit issued by Czech authorities in order to stay in Czech Republic legally. There are a few types of residence permits issued by the Czech authorities.

Short-term and long-term visa

In Czech legislation the distinction is made between long-term visas and short-term visas. The first include the visas for periods of up to 90 days long, and the latter the visas for longer stays. The rules of granting short-term visas in Czechia vary for different countries' nationals and are dependent on the legislative framework applying to the particular states. Analysing those frameworks in a detailed manner is clearly beyond the scope of this report, thus it is enough to say that more information on this subject can be found in the website of MI (MI, Department for Asylum and Migration Policy 2020 a).

As has already been mentioned, short-term visas are issued to the non-Schengen countries' nationals for a maximum period of 90 days within any 180 days period. There is a list of countries, however, whose nationals are, according to Schengen Area regulations, exempt from visa requirements (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Czech Republic 2021). Visa-free regime applies to foreigners whose purpose of stay is different from employment. That detail, after the visa-free movement had been introduced with Ukraine in 2017, appears as a quite important issue regarding the regional context of central Europe, as unregistered work performed by third country nationals residing there on the basis of tourist visas is hard to control and account for statistical purposes.

Long-term visas in Czechia can be issued to foreigners for various purposes, among them: studies, business, family, sports and culture and collecting a residence permit. Apart from those, Czech government has also set up a legislative solution named 'special work visa', allowing itself to extend visa-eligibility to migrants of particular professions and nationalities for limited periods of time. Such extensions can be introduced in line with specific, relevant, government regulations where the desirable citizenships and sector criteria are to be identified (MI 2021 c).

A long term residence permit

According to MI, the foreigners entitled to being granted with the long-term residence permits in Czech Republic, which is a first type of residence we are going to recall, have to meet the three criteria, first of which is that they should have been residing in the territory of the state for more than 90 days visa-basis by the time they apply. Secondly, they are expected to intend to reside in Czechia for at least 12 months, with the time they had already spent in the country by the date of filing an application included within this period. The exceptions for 90-days rule can be made, for example, for the holders of employee card, blue card-holders or families of scientists employed in Czech Republic.

The purpose of issuing a long term residence certificate must be determined in the process of application in accordance with the list of purposes acknowledged by MI. Among those, for example, the following ones are included: education, job seeking, conducting scientific research, entrepreneurship or family reunification. For each of those the requirements are specified in the MI website, as they differ substantially one from another. The long-term residence permits may also be issued to EU Blue Card holders (Ministry of Foreign affairs of the Czech Republic 2021). Since 2014 it is not possible to apply for a long term residence permit on a basis of employment, as such an instrument has been withdrawn and replaced by so-called employee cards (MI 2020 a).

An employee card

According to Czech MI, an employee card is a 'new type of permit for long-time residence in the territory of the Czech Republic (CR) where the purpose of the foreign national's stay (longer than 3 months) is employment' (MI 2021 d). The cards are issued for a foreigner to work for a particular employer determined during the application procedure. However their maximal period of validity is 2 years, they might be extended repeatedly.

It is worth highlighting that foreign nationals residing in Czechia on a basis of employee cards are allowed to change their places of employment under some conditions. However that might seem obvious, it is not always the case. For example, foreigners residing and working in neighbouring Poland on the basis of 'Temporary residence and work permit' (in Polish: 'Jednolite zezwolenie na pobyt i pracę') are forced to apply for a new permit every time they change employers. Moreover they are allowed to reside in the territory of Poland only for a limited period of 30 days after their initial employment terminates (Urząd do Spraw Cudzoziemców 2021).

That, obviously, undermines the stability and safety of foreign workers residing in the country, curbing their opportunities to seek better employment and living conditions, and thus limiting chances of upwards social mobility. Similar procedure applies to employees working in Czechia, however the period when jobless foreigners are forced to find new employment is extended twofold, to 60 days, in contrast to the regulation introduced in Poland. Thereupon, however the very dual nature of the employee card, as it connects maintaining employment of a foreigner with their right to reside in the country, is in itself controversial, the specific regulations it concerns are more favourable for foreign workers than those witnessed in some other countries of the region. For clarity it should be also highlighted that the employment cards might be also issued as non-dual, residence document, in cases where the employment permission is obtained by the foreigners on another basis.

A permanent residence permit

A permanent residence certificate can be issued to foreign national who has continuously been residing in the Czech Republic for a period of at least five years. Within the procedure, the 'legal status of a long-term resident' is being recognized with regard to the applicant. It is acknowledged provided the applicant meets three criteria. The first of them is the already-mentioned period of continuous residence in the country, the second is the lack of indication that the applicant had engaged in activities threatening the national security of any of the EU countries or that they have been acting in a way that would threaten the public order. The third criterion is that the applicant must demonstrate they are financially capable of residing in Czech Republic on a permanent-basis (MI 2021 a).

Another group entitled to applying for permanent residence permits in Czech Republic are the EU Blue Card holders, who are obligated to prove they had lived in the EU for at least five years and out of those at least two they had spent in Czechia.

What seems crucially important from migrant workers' point of view is that the permanent residence permit grants the employed migrants the access to the state healthcare for their children, as Czechia is the only country in the European Union which denies the third country nationals employed in its territory the access to the public medical care for their kids as long as they do not hold a permanent residence permit (as of September 2020) (*Czech Republic: New initiative...* 2020).

Legalisation of employment in the Czech Republic

Since the accession to the European Union in 2004 the Czech Republic is a part of EURES network facilitating international mobility of labour. The administrative unit that manages the EURES participation of Czech Republic locally is the Labour Office of the Czech Republic (Urad prace CR 2020 a). The administrative unit in charge of foreigners' employment in the Czech Republic is the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs (hereafter: MoLSA) (MoLSA 2019).

According to the law of the Czech Republic many groups of foreigners are not obliged to apply for a work permit. EU/EEA member states' citizens, the EU nationals' family members, foreign nationals holding

permanent residence in Czech Republic and asylum seekers are entitled to take up the legal employment in the country without applying for for this kind of document and they 'have the same legal standing regarding employment as Czech citizens, and therefore are unlimited in the work they can do, with the exception of a very few positions that require Czech citizenship by law.' (Euraxess, Researchers in Motion 2021). The 'family members of EU citizens who are not themselves EU citizens may work [in the Czech Republic] without a work permit only once they have obtained a residence permit as a family member of an EU citizen from the Ministry of the Interior.' (Euraxess, Researchers in Motion 2021).

On the other hand for those foreigners who do have to apply for a work permit to be legally employed in Czechia the situation differs:

EU membership in 2004 created a new division for foreign workers: those coming from other EU Member States and third-country nationals. While EU nationals can work freely in Czechia, third-country nationals face demanding administrative and bureaucratic requirements, including labor market tests and the need to obtain visas and work permits. (Drbohlav and Janurová 2019)

Until 2014, it had been possible to be legally employed in Czechia on a basis of a long term residence permit issued with a specific purpose of employment. Currently, however, as has been already mentioned in this report, that instrument is not in use anymore and the foreigners who are not members of any of the previously listed groups have to apply for the employee card in order to be permitted to find a legal employment in Czechia. Next to the employee card, another two legal pathways to finding a legal employment in the Czech Republic are the EU blue card or internationally transferable employee card. Then, only holding a valid residence permit and being granted one of the two, listed documents the foreigner may apply for a work permit in Czechia (Urad Prace 2020 b).

Picture: Jan Baborak/Unsplash.com

5. The Czech Diaspora

Central Europe witnessed a few centuries of intensive cultural and language diffusion, and what we nowadays recognise as the pattern of borders separating the territories of Poland, Hungary, Czechia, Slovakia and Germany was determined a relatively short time ago. Therefore, recognising a particular group of people as the ethnic descendants and inheritors of a given national community in Central-European context often proves difficult, if not impossible. As the region has undergone numerous political transformations not only in the 20th, but also in the previous centuries, acknowledging an individual as a member of the diaspora community connected to one the currently existing national states is often possible only adopting the subjective lens of its interests.

Between 1948 and 1989 between 200 000 and 500 000 people left the former Czechoslovakia. A great share of them were high-skilled migrants who relatively easily adapted to the life in their new countries of residence, gradually losing both their connection to the country of origin as well as Czechoslovak citizenships. Thus, those people might fall outside of the diaspora statistics we are interested in for the purposes of this report (Jungwirth et al 2019: 18). Nevertheless, there are some estimations and numbers worth mentioning. For the purposes of this part of the report we are using mostly the information gathered from the article published by Dušan Drbohlav and Kristýna Janurová: 'Migration and Integration in Czechia: Policy Advances and the Hand Brake of Populism' (2019).

In 2017 there were almost 1 million Czech citizenship-holders living in different countries around the world. A big share in this group were those Czech nationals who had left their country of origin after the fall of socialism in the 90's. Another big outflow of people from Czech Republic took place after the country's accession to the European Union in 2004 (a similar phenomenon has been witnessed in the neighbouring Poland). On the other hand the number of the members of diaspora when this term is understood more broadly, as 'those who claim Czech origins or ancestry, sometimes going back centuries', is much bigger (Drbohlav and Janurová 2019). In 2012 the size of this group was estimated as approximately 2.5 million. Among them 1,6 million are Czech (or Czechoslovak) ancestors living in the USA. Then, there are 105 000 people claiming Czech origins in Canada and 40 000 of those who find themselves ethnic Czechoslovaks. As of 2017, 55 000 people living in the United Kingdom were born in Czech Republic, with 49 000 of them holding passports issued by the Czech Republic. Finally, the three other important emigration destinations for Czechs are the Slovak Republic, where 35 000 people live for whom Czech is a native language, Germany with 50 000 Czechs living in the country, and Austria, with the same number of Czechs (Drbohlav and Janurová 2019).

Obviously, together with a major change in the political reality, the motivations for emigration changed for Czechs. As Drbohlav and Janurová (2019) point out, while in the time around WWII and in the later decades, before the collapse of the communist regime, the most important drivers of outward migration were of political nature. Then, after the borders had opened enabling people to move abroad freely, more people started to migrate from Czech Republic seeking better education. Currently it is assumed that most of the migration from Czechia is the temporary movement:

The few studies that have analyzed Czech emigration show that many Czech migrants prefer temporary mobility targeted at the accumulation of financial capital, language skills, or international experience to be used for one's social or economic mobility in Czechia upon return. Although data are lacking, it is assumed that temporary migration extending from a few months to a couple of years forms a large part of Czech international mobility. (Drbohlav and Janurová 2019)

Since the beginning of the 90's the Czech Republic has been maintaining its diaspora policy, however, as Drbohlav and Janurová point in the cited source (2019), apart from a variety of cultural and educational events, the state's activity in this field has been scant. The objectives of this policy have been introduced by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Czech Republic as follows:

The Czech foreign policy will focus not only on working with traditional compatriot communities formed in the wake of emigration during the 19th and 20th centuries in particular, but also on expats who have acquired a permanent or long-term residence abroad as a result of more widespread international mobility on the globalised international stage. Similarly, Czech foreign policy intends to make more use of the community of foreign nationals who have settled permanently or long term in the Czech Republic as they are in a position to help spread the reputation of the Czech Republic in their countries of origin. (2015: 12)

Recently, the Czech Ministry of Foreign affairs decided to introduce a new, annual holiday: the official 'Day of Czechs abroad', when the state plans to celebrate its relationship with the diaspora (Czech Republic to introduce... 2020).

Picture: Jonas Jacobsson/Unsplash.com

6. Migration flows and stock

6.1 The number of migrants in Czechia and general statistics

Before moving to the analysis of the Czech migration flows and stock it is worth reminding that the statistics concerning migrants are susceptible to statistical biases due to the general vulnerability, invisibility and a tendency to be socially excluded of this group. In the Czech context, for example, Černá and colleagues point out that due to the partial invisibility of unregistered migrants' population in the statistics, the number of foreigners residing in Czech Republic might be even twice as big as the official counts suggest (Černá et al. 2021: 6) while, Drbohlav and Janurová (2019) estimate the number of unregistered migrants in Czechia to be somewhere between 15 000 to 300 000, depending on the 'type of irregularity studied' (2019). Therefore, all the analyses conducted for the purposes of this report, as they are based on official statistics, should be understood as rough estimates and treated with the necessary precautions.

In the data we utilise for the purposes of this analysis, gathered mostly from the Czech Statistical Office, the most important concept used to describe a group of immigrants are 'foreigners'. 'The foreigner' in Czech statistical context is understood simply as someone who does not hold Czech citizenship. Foreigners, then, might reside on the territory of the Czech Republic on a temporary or on a permanent basis, in accordance with the residence permits' regime described in the previous parts of this report. Importantly, Czech statisticians refer to the UN framework for international statistics from 1998, indicating, that according to those recommendations, the change of usual residence is assumed to have occurred for an individual after they reside in a foreign country for at least a year.

Since the early 90s' the overall population of Czech Republic grew by approximately 300 000 people. There were almost 10 700 000 people in Czechia in 2019 (Czech Statistical Office 2019 a) and according to the preliminary data for 2020 the population is expected to have exceeded that number in 2020 (Czech Statistical Office 2021 d). The latest change in the direction of the trend in population change occurred in 2003, after a decade of population's shrinkage between 1994 and 2002. Since then, with the exception of 2013, each year brought an increase in the number of people residing in Czech Republic (Czech Statistical Office 2019 b).

What should be highlighted is that the inflow of migrants played a much more important role in reversing the downward tendency than the domestic changes. Of all the immigrant groups, the Ukrainians played a key role in boosting the Czech population (Migration boosted... 2019), which, on 1st of January 2021 totalled to 10 706 534 (Czech Republic population 2021). The natural increase rate for Czechia, as highlighted by Drbohlav and Janurová, declined from 2008 to 2018 substantially (2019), as a result of the severe demographic crisis witnessed by all the CEE countries. Meanwhile, between 1993 and 2017, the share of immigrants in overall population of Czechia rose from less than 1% to almost 5%, and the yearly number of live births of foreigners has been steadily rising, from above 2500 in 2008, to over 4500 in 2019 (Czech Statistical Office 2020 b). The present and future inflow of migrants to Czechia, as well as to the other countries of the Visegrad Group, might be a crucial factor with regard to upkeeping the central-European economy, considering that according to United Nations' prognoses populations all four of V4 member states are going to shrink over a few, next decades, with Czechia losing 5.5% of its population (Central Europe's population... 2018).

Nevertheless, it should be highlighted that however immigration ratio for Czechia has been rising, the predictions of experts indicate that the very future immigration occurring in a scale that can be realistically anticipated is not going to be able to reverse the overall demographic trends. The biggest effect that can be expected is the inflow of foreigners possibly alleviating some outcomes of the negative demographic trends:

[T]o offset the assumed changes of any parameter characterizing the age structure and its ageing by migration is de facto impossible even in a short term perspective since the estimated needs in net-migration inflows stay fully outside any reality. There is no doubt that migration in the Czech Republic context is not able to prevent or even cure population of demographic ageing. All that migration of realistic dimension can do is to offset expected population decline caused by the insufficient natural reproduction and slightly reduce the most radical demonstrations of the demographic ageing process (Burcin et al. 2005: 65).

The same statement can be made with regard to the broader, European context. According to Fihel and colleagues:

[I]n order for the European population to remain at the same level during the period of 1995-2050, 100 million immigrants would have to arrive in the continent. In order to maintain the level of the working age population -161 million. In order to keep the ratio of working age population to the old people below three - 235 million people would have to arrive. [...]. In long term immigration does not stop the process of ageing of the society nor the shrinking of its working age population <Coleman 2002>, but it can curb the demographic shortages (or labour force dearth) on ad hoc basis <Howse 2006> (Fihel et al. 2017: 186-187)¹.

The number of foreign residents in the country amounted to 634 790 in 2020 (Czech Statistical Office 2021 d), while the net migration rate for Czechia has been reported as almost 27 000. Last year over 55 000 people arrived in the country, and close to 29 000 people left. The net migration rate in 2020 has thus been approximately 40% smaller than during the previous year. In comparison with 2019 approximately 15% less immigrants arrived to the country and 35% more emigrated (Czech Statistical Office 2021 h)².

According to Drbohlav and Janurová, in 2019 almost 40% of immigrants lived in the country's capital. Other popular destinations for foreign nationals residing in Czechia were big cities and areas close to the country's border (2019). According to the data for that year, it can also be said that almost 43% of migrants in the country at the time were women (Czech Statistical Office 2021 f). The feminisation rate among the immigrants is quite significant, however lower than among the general Czech population in which women make up 50,8% of the population (Population, female (% of total population)... 2021). Interestingly, the share of women differed between the group of migrants staying in Czechia permanently and the group of migrants residing in the country on the basis of other forms of stay. For the first group the feminisation rate amounted to about 47% and for the latter to merely about 38% (Czech Statistical Office 2019 c). The changing gender ratio and overall number of migrants living in the country are presented in the chart below:

¹ Translated by the authors from Polish: 'Na przykład, aby utrzymać ludność Europy na stałym poziomie, w okresie 1995-2050 musiałyby napłynąć 100 milionów imigrantów, aby utrzymać liczbę ludności w wieku produkcyjnym – 161 milionów, aby zaś utrzymać stosunek ludności w wieku produkcyjnym do ludności starszej poniżej trzech – 235 milionów [...]. W dłuższej perspektywie zatem imigracja nie powstrzymuje procesu starzenia się społeczeństwa ani zmniejszania się zasobów siły roboczej <Coleman, 2002>, ale może uzupełniać braki demograficzne (czy też siły roboczej) w sposób doraźny <Howse, 2006> (Fihel & Górny & Kudła & Walczyk 2017: 186-187).'

² The net migration rate is calculated in accordance with the definitions introduced by the Czech Statistical Office, where the immigrants and emigrants (in the database: *In-/Out-migrants and Immigrants/Emigrants with registered residence*) are such persons who hold a long-term or a permanent residence permit in a reference period.

Figure 1. Migrants in Czechia, gender distribution in migrants' group, December 2010 - December 2020.
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

Between 2010 and 2019 the number of foreigners permanently or long-term resided in Czechia grew by almost 30%, to reach 593 366 in 2019. Higher increase has been observed in the number of foreigners holding permanent residence than among those holding long-term resident permits. The size of the first group changed from 188 952 to 299 453 (approximately 58% increase), while the size of the latter increased from 235 339 in 2010 to 293 913 in 2019 (increase of around 25%) (Czech Statistical Office 2021 e).

Figure 2. Permanent and other types of stay, September 2011 - September 2020.
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

As indicated by the figure below, members of the biggest national group among migrants residing in Czechia - the Ukrainians - more frequently hold permanent rather than temporary forms of stay permits. Slovaks - second largest group of foreigners residing in the country - slightly more often reside in Czechia on the basis of non-permanent residence permits. Interestingly, on the other hand, the situation looks very much different for the Vietnamese. The nationals of that country who reside in the Czech Republic on a basis of permanent residence permit outnumber those residing in a country on a basis of other forms of stay fivefold.

Figure 3. The nine biggest immigrant groups in Czechia by type of stay (as at 31 December 2020).
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2020 A).

As it has already been stated, the largest national group among migrants residing in the Czech Republic are Ukrainians (about 165 000 people at the end of 2020). Their number has increased by above 33% between December 2010 and December 2020. The second biggest group of migrants in Czechia are Slovaks. In December of 2020 about 124 000 of them lived in the country, in contrast to approximately 72 000 at the end of 2010. That indicates roughly 72% increase over the last decade. Other largest national groups of foreign residents of Czechia at the end of 2020 included immigrants from Vietnam (almost 63 000 in 2020), Russia (almost 42 000 in the same year), Germany and Poland (the last two groups ones around 21 000 each). The sizes of those immigrant groups have also been increasing throughout the last decade.

Figure 4. The increase in the size of the six biggest immigrant groups in Czech Republic, December 2010 - December 2020.
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

Among the six largest national groups of immigrants in Czechia, relatively to the size of a group, the biggest increase between September 2011 and September 2020 has been witnessed among Slovaks, as in 2020 there were 54% more of them residing in Czechia than in 2011. Then, between September 2011 and September 2020, the group of Ukrainian immigrants in the Czech Republic grew in size by 45%, a group of Germans by 36%, the Russians by 35%, while for the Vietnamese and Poles, respectively, 12% and 8% rises were witnessed. What seems more interesting, however, is that whilst for the overall population of immigrants in Czechia the 51% increase in size have occurred in the previous decade, this rate for an overall group of nationalities other than the six most numerous ones, reaches much higher value. As, comparatively to 2011, in 2020 92% more individuals not registered as Slovaks, Ukrainians, Germans, Russians, Vietnamese or Poles were known to reside in Czechia, it might be said that the overall group of immigrants living in Czechia is becoming more nationally diverse (see figure 4).

Figure 5. Changes in a size of the biggest national groups among immigrants in Czechia between September 2011 and September 2020.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

Similar conclusion one may draw from analysing changes in the distribution of nationalities in the overall number of migrants living in the Czech Republic over the last ten years. Among six largest immigrant groups present in Czechia, only the Slovaks insignificantly increased their share in an overall group of foreign residents in the country. As one may see in the figure 5 the relative declines of the shares of Ukrainians, Vietnamese, Russians, Poles and Germans in the overall migrants' group (between September 2011 and 2020) oscillated between less than 1% and slightly over 3%. At the same time, the relative share of nationalities other than the aforementioned rose by almost 7%, which proves that the national diversity of immigrants in Czechia is increasing.

Figure 6. Changes in the distribution of nationalities in the overall group of immigrants in Czechia, September 2011 to September 2020.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

As it has already been said, the biggest group of immigrants living in Czechia are the Ukrainian nationals. The growing presence of Ukrainian nationals in Czechia is linked with the economic situation in Ukraine as well as with geographical, cultural and historical proximity between the countries. Also the Russian annexation of the Crimea and a partially successful attempt to invade and occupy East Ukraine substantially impacted the immigration patterns of Ukrainian to Czechia (as well as other countries of the V4 region) in the last decade.

Figure 7. Change in the number of Ukrainians and Slovaks in Czechia between June 2010 and June 2021.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

As pointed out by many migration scholars focusing on Central and Eastern Europe, the war and uncertainty of the political situation in Ukraine have been important push factors for many young Ukrainians who left the country over the last decade (Leontiyeva & Kopecká 2018: 8). On the other hand, Zdeněk Uherek sheds a different light on this issue, pointing to the changes in the structure of types of residence documents held by the Ukrainian nationals in the Czech Republic. The Czech scholar stresses, that while, according to him, the war in Ukraine had not itself caused the number of Ukrainian migrants to rise, it might have had, to some extent, shifted the patterns of applications for residence permits in the group of Ukrainians:

The total number of citizens of Ukraine in the Czech Republic did not dramatically increase as a result of the war events. In the area of long-term and permanent residences, we can rather observe a stagnation in the total number of Ukrainian citizens. This points not to development influenced by war events but to the situation in the labour market in the Czech Republic, where the revival of the economy in areas where Ukrainian employees found employment took place rather slowly [...].

As we observed in the course of the oil crisis in the Western states in the 1970s (Castles & Miller 1993), also in the case of Ukrainian migration to the Czech Republic the crisis situation led to efforts of foreign employees to stabilise their position in the target country and create such conditions that the possible loss of employment did not threaten their stay there (Castles 1986). [...] [T]he crisis [...] meant a change in the structure of the stays [in the Czech Republic]. While long-term stays still dominated over permanent residences in 2011, Ukrainian migrants still more clearly prefer permanent residences. This indicates their becoming stabilised in the country and that the majority of Ukrainian migrants have decided to live in the Czech Republic. The flexible workforce, which came to the Czech Republic mainly for earnings to be used in Ukraine, is becoming a category of foreigners who set down roots in the Czech Republic (Uherek 2016: 7-8).

It should also be pointed out that the abolition of visa requirement for Ukrainians in June 2017 had an impact both on the structure of residence permits held by the nationals of this country and on the very number of migrants from Ukraine arriving in the Czech Republic. Since the introduction of this change in the entry requirements in 2017 the Ukrainians made 33 million trips to the Schengen countries, within two years. According to the Ukrainian diplomatic mission to the EU more than 2.5 million of these trips were visa-free (Ukrainians and Moldovans are... 2020).

Finally, it is clear that not only the Ukrainian nationals have been eager to migrate to Czechia over the last few years, but also the Czech authorities have anticipated possible advantages in their influx to the country. Just to illustrate this claim, it might be enough to say that in 2018 the Czech government doubled the number of fast-track employment permits issued to Ukrainians from 19 600 per year (Czech government raises... 2018), just to 40 000 a year after (Czech Republic doubles... 2019). Those changes have been a part of a wider attempt of Czech authorities to increase the number of labour migrants in the country, simplifying and shortening procedures for hiring foreign nationals by the Czech employers:

From 2018, there was the 'Regime Ukraine' with a doubled annual capacity standing at 19,600, 'Regime Mongolia', 'Regime Philippines' and more recently also a 'Regime Serbia' (each at 1,000 persons per year) plus the 'Pilot Project Ukraine' for highly qualified workers with an annual quota of 500 (Jungwirth et al. 2019: 20-21).

The Czech authorities have closely monitored the employment regulations introduced by neighbouring Poland. According to the Polish Office for Foreigners, Czech Labour market witnessed substantial inflow of such Ukrainian workers who had obtained their residence permits in Poland:

By the end of 2016, 119 thousand Ukrainians were legally staying in Czechia. For the last few months the Czech labour market has been witnessing the inflow of Ukrainian nationals holding Polish-visas, who find employment there through the agency of Polish companies. Most of them (a few thousand) hold Polish short-term employment visas issued within the system of declarations on entrusting work to a foreigner³ and gets sent there by Polish recruitment agencies. Some of the Ukrainian workers reside in the Czech Republic as posted workers hired by Polish employers (OSW, Centre for Eastern Studies 2017: 8)⁴.

Trčka and colleagues (2018: 48-49) place the group of Ukrainian workers on a blurred line between legal and illegal employment. The researchers from the Multicultural Centre Prague underline, that such migrants are placed closer to the 'legitimate pole' than, for example, the tourist-visa workers, but also point out, that the Czech government perceives such foreigners as being 'falsely posted' on a basis of a 'hidden intermediation of employment', thus illegally employed. Therefore Trčka and his co-workers stress that the internalised awareness of residing in a foreign country on a basis of a semi-legal status might increase the feeling of uncertainty and fear in foreign employees. It might also stop them from claiming their rights and entitlements or hold them back from reaching out for institutional support. In consequence, it should be highlighted that the Ukrainian workers employed in the Czech Republic on a basis of visas issued in Poland might be in a particularly vulnerable position of the local labour market (Ibidem).

³ *Vide:* Chwat O., Brzozowski J., Sikorska J. (2021). *Report on migration and demographic patterns in Poland*, CASPAR – Center for Advanced Studies of Population and Religion, Cracow University of Economics, p. 4.

⁴ Translated by the authors from Polish from: "Pod koniec 2016 roku 119 tysięcy Ukraińców przebywało w Czechach legalnie. Od kilku miesięcy na czeskim rynku pracy rośnie liczba obywateli Ukrainy z polskimi wizami, którzy trafiają do Czech za pośrednictwem polskich firm. Zdecydowana większość (kilka tysięcy) legitymuje się polską wizą do pracy krótkoterminowej wydaną w ramach systemu oświadczeń i jest wysyłana do Czech przez polskie agencje pracy. Część ukraińskich migrantów przebywa w Czechach również w charakterze pracowników delegowanych przez polskich pracodawców."

Picture: Fernando Lavin/Unsplash.com

According to Drbohlav and Janurová, the predominant purpose of immigration to Czechia is of economic nature, however, what we point out in the data below, the number of foreign students undertaking education in the country has also been on the rise over the last couple of years. What seems important from a demographic point of view, the migrants' group is relatively young, with almost 80% of them being economically active:

Most migrants come for jobs and opportunity, with 45 percent in 2017 citing employment or entrepreneurship and 20 percent studies as migration motives (some 44,000 foreigners studied at Czech universities). Just 27 percent came for family reasons. As a result of the primacy of work and study reasons for migration, 77 percent are in the economically active age (20-59). Of this age grouping, the younger cohort aged 20 – 39 represents 42 percent of all migrants. In contrast, those over age 65 are just 5 percent of all migrants (Drbohlav & Janurová 2019).

6.2 Employment of foreigners in Czechia

As the unemployment rate in the Czech Republic over the last couple of years has remained one of the lowest in Europe, the issue of shortages in the labour force, similar to the situation in neighbouring Poland, became a problem for the local economy. According to the OECD data for 2020, Czechia had the fifth highest employment rate of all the European Union countries, and the second lowest unemployment rate (after Poland). What is more, the employment of third country nationals in Czechia, according to the data for 2018, reached the highest value out of all the EU countries, topping the EU average by over 21 percentage points and coming up to 78,8% (Czech Republic: Statistics... 2018).

Figure 8. Employment rate as the percentage of working age population in Visegrad Group Countries, 2015-2020. Source: OECD (2021 a).

Figure 9. Share of unemployed working age population in V4 Countries, 2015-2020.
Source: OECD (2021 b).

According to the analysis of Jungwirth and colleagues (based on the data from the Czech Statistical Office for 2015), the majority of foreigners residing that year in the Czech Republic - almost 48% - have been employed in mid-qualified jobs, less than 29% worked in low qualified jobs, and almost 24% have been working in highly qualified jobs. Interestingly, this distribution looked almost identical for both the EU nationals' group as well as for the group of third country nationals (Jungwirth et al. 2019: 23). Having analysed the data on foreigners' employment disaggregated by particular sectors of the economy, the researchers drew also the following conclusions, regarding the sector distribution of foreigners employment:

EU nationals most often work in Manufacturing (over 90,000 in 2016), followed by Administrative and support service activities (47,000), Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (28,000), Construction (25,000) and Professional, scientific and technical activities (20,000). Similarly, third country-nationals most often held jobs in Manufacturing (22,000), after which came Administrative and support service activities (13,000), Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (12,000), Construction (12,000), and Accommodation and food service activities (10,000). When compared to the general population, migrants in the Czech Republic have a higher presence in administrative and support service activities, manufacturing, construction or professional, scientific and technical activities (Ibidem).

Jungwirth and colleagues stressed also that, apart from providing support for the IT industry, the labour of foreigners residing in the Czech Republic is also of substantial importance for the Czech healthcare system, as migrants provide support both in institutional healthcare context, as well as working as private caregivers (Ibidem).

6.3 Foreigners in the Czech educational system

According to Kugiel and Pędziwiatr, Czech Universities witness a process of internationalisation, attracting an increasing number of foreign students. One of the major pull factors for foreigners undertaking higher education in the Czech Republic is the unrestricted access to the local labour market for international students (Kugiel & Pędziwiatr 2021). However, as indicated by the data presented below, between 2009 and 2019 the number of foreigners engaged in the process of education in Czechia has been on the rise for all educational levels. The biggest increase has been witnessed in the nursery schools, as the number of foreign-born preschoolers in Czechia increased threefold over that period. Then, the number of primary school students increased by over 90%, the number of foreigners in higher education by 34%, and the number of secondary school students by 20% (see figure 10).

Figure 10. Foreigners in education in the Czech Republic by the level of education⁵.
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 j).

The recent decade saw a major increase in the number and in the share of third-country nationals among all foreigners undertaking higher education in the Czech Republic. While in 2010 27% of foreign students in the Czech Republic were of non-EU28 nationality, in 2013 this rate had grown to almost 34%, to reach nearly 40% after the next three years. The most recent data available for 2019 indicate that the share of third country nationals in the overall number of foreigners educating at the Czech universities exceeds 45%:

Figure 11. Foreign students from the European Union and from the third countries.
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 i).

Unsurprisingly, the largest national group among foreign students in the Czech Republic are Slovaks, almost fourfold outnumbering the Russians, who form the next biggest group of foreign citizens studying in Czechia. As one may see on the figure below their number, has been though decreasing from almost 25 thousand in 2010 to slightly above 21 thousand a decade later.

⁵ The 'higher education' category includes university students (46 441 in 2019/20 academic year), higher professional school students (732 students in the same year) and conservatoire students (2019 in 2019/20).

Figure 12. Slovaks in Czech Universities, 2010-2019.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 i).

Apart from the two aforementioned groups, other nationalities present in significant numbers among foreign students in Czechia are the Ukrainians, whose number more than doubled over the last decade, Kazakhs, constituting the fourth largest foreign students' group in Czechia, Indians, Germans and Belarussians.

Figure 13. Foreigners in Czech Universities, top 6 nationalities without Slovaks.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 i).

6.4 Citizenship acquisitions

Third country nationals residing in Czechia might be granted Czech citizenship after 5 years of uninterrupted stay, while for the EU citizens this period is reduced to three years. However, there is also a comprehensive list of exemptions from those rules. Apart from the requirement concerning the length of previous residence, among others, applicant's legal and financial situation, as well as their knowledge of Czech language and cultural context are assessed (MI 2021 b).

According to the MI data published by Jirsa and Šťastný, Ukrainian passport has been held by more than 30% of persons who obtained Czech citizenship in 2018. Among the persons naturalised the Ukrainians make up the largest group. More than 16% of those who acquired Czech citizenship held Russian passports, 13% were Slovak, and about 6% Vietnamese. The smaller groups were constituted by Belarussians, Moldavians, Romanians, Poles, Kazakhs and Serbians. Almost 80% of all those who acquired Czech citizenship were third country nationals (Jirsa & Šťastný 2020: 87-88).

The substantial increase in the number of Czech citizenships acquired by foreigners has been witnessed in 2014, after the Act No 186/201 Sb on Czech Citizenship had been introduced. According to this legislation, among other changes, holding a dual citizenship is now fully legalised for Czech citizens, and acquiring a Czech citizenship, for example for the second-generation migrants, has been eased (Czech Statistical Office 2021 g):

Figure 14. Citizenships acquired by foreigners in Czechia (2010-2019).

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2019 c).

6.5 International protection

The legal framework for international protection in Czechia is the 'Asylum Act and Act on the Residence of Foreign Nationals' from 1999 (Parliament of the Czech Republic 1999), with numerous amendments adopted later, the latest in 2015. As it has been mentioned in introductory part of this report, the institutional body responsible for shaping asylum policy in Czechia is the Ministry of Interior, which, as has been already stated in this paper, maintains such agenda towards immigrants which could be colloquially described as suspicious and ill-affected, if not hostile.

Apparently, those immigrants who experience the outcomes of this attitude the most, are the asylum seekers. In the major strategic document institutionalized by Czech authorities, 'the Czech Republic 2030 - Strategic framework' (in Czech: Strategický rámec Česká republika 2030), the migrants that the Czech authorities prefer to welcome in the country are: 'young and highly qualified white-collars from culturally and linguistically close countries' (Czech Republic 2030... 2017). Most of the asylum seekers do not fall within this category and clearly a number of obstacles and difficulties they face arriving in Czechia is a result of the aforementioned general approach of the authorities. It is worth mentioning that, according to Eurostat data from 2018, the Czech Republic has been the country where the rate of successful applications has been the lowest of all the EU countries, as it totalled to approximately 10% with no single migrant being relocated in the country that year (Svobodova 2019).

As already mentioned in this report, none of the external, land borders of Czechia is the external border of the European Union. However, asylum seekers might arrive in the country through one of the Czech airports (European Commission, European Migration Network 2019: 5). Similarly to the situation of asylum seekers in the neighbouring Poland (Mrowicki 2020), those arriving in Czechia who seek refuge commonly face different forms of harassment from the representatives of the state. Many comprehensive reports, as well as statements of individual refugees prove that asylum seekers' cases in Czechia (similarly to Poland and Hungary) are commonly proceeded in defiance of international law, not to mention the very concept of compassion grounded in principles of the ethical system that serves as the underpinning for the European solidarity and European Union as a political body itself.

It should be highlighted that the Alien Police of the Czech Republic (the force that is responsible for patrolling Czech borders) has been reported to make it difficult for persons seeking international protection to file such applications. Moreover, the internationally accepted *non-refoulement* principle is known to have been repeatedly breached by the authorities, while the screenings of foreigners arriving in the country have been described as 'catastrophical, systemic failure' (Hungarian Helsinki Committee 2017: 7-8). The testimonies of clients of Organization for Aid to Refugees include such stories as the one of the man who has been imprisoned in Czechia for a couple of months after arriving in the country with forged documents, regardless that those had been the only way for him to flee his home country - Sri Lanka. After arriving at the airport in Prague the man who had previously experienced tortures and persecution in his country of residence has not been allowed to use the toilet, nor has been granted anything to drink or eat. After a few hours, when the Tamil-speaking interpreter arrived, the man was informed he is not allowed to file an application for asylum. The legal procedures undertaken by the Czech authorities have not been explained to the foreigner, therefore he did not comprehend a rationale behind the course of events that led to his imprisonment. While staying in the arrest, for five months the man has not been allowed to leave the building where he has been kept. Over that period he has often been receiving such food that he could not consume due to principles of his faith and when he became severely ill, presumably in result of poor living conditions in the cell, he had been told he would have to pay for medicines that he had been given. Shortly after that, the medication he has been receiving stopped (Hungarian Helsinki Committee 2017: 9-10). Needless to say, the major concern for those engaged in supporting asylum seekers in the region have also been recurrent cases of putting immigrant minors in detention (European Asylum Support Office 2021: 12-13).

The authors of this report mention those stories in order to give examples of inhumane treatment experienced by the asylum seekers arriving in the central-European countries, Czechia among them. It should be stressed that the NGOs, the representatives of the civil society and all other formal and informal bodies engaged in securing human rights of asylum seekers in the region have now for many years been in an unequal fight attempting to alleviate the dreadful consequences of agendas implemented by right-wing governments of the particular, national states of the region. Regretfully, in 2021 this struggle is ongoing.

As indicated by the data from the Czech Statistical Office, the number of applications for international protection in Czech Republic in the period of 1990-2019 totalled to 76 336, with 16 725 applications filed by the Ukrainian nationals, 3904 of them between 2015 and 2019. This number is clearly connected to the ongoing military conflict in the Eastern Ukraine and Russian annexation of Crimea.

Table 1. Applications for international protection and positive decisions concerning granting an asylum and granting subsidiary protection by citizenship of the applicant or grantee (top countries by number of applicants for international protection).

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 a, b, c).

Country	Number of applications for international protection (1998-2019) ⁶	Decisions of asylum granting (2004 - 2019)	Decisions of subsidiary protection granting (2006 -2019)
Ukraine	16 725	180	402
Russia	9 485	309	91
Vietnam	5 285	17	10
Moldova	4 563	26	4
Slovakia	3 928	0	<i>no data</i>
Georgia	3 463	25	7
India	3 010	2	<i>no data</i>
China	2 940	22	12
Armenia	2 900	75	12
Romania	2 608	0	<i>no data</i>
Belarus	2 420	241	261
Afghanistan	1 820	55	63
Mongolia	1 481	6	1
Iraq	1 368	160	217
Kazachstan	1 281	97	140
Turkey	1 097	14	<i>no data</i>

Then, as indicated by the data presented in the table 3 below , Czechia did not witness the asylum applications number to spike in the period around 2015, when that has been a case for many other European countries receiving increased numbers of third country nationals seeking refuge. Jungwirth attributes that to: the fact that none of the borders of Czechia is an external Schengen border, relatively low attractiveness of the country for immigrants seeking international protection, and finally to the repressiveness of policies introduced in the country, in particular to 'broad use of administrative detention for transiting migrants <OHCHR 2015> (Jungwirth et al 2019: 15)'.

⁶ The year refers to the date when the proceeding of the application commenced.

As it has been already pointed out by the authors of this report, the rate of positive decisions among all asylum application cases filed in the Czech Republic is relatively low, reaching less than 8% in 2019. That is even less than a year before, when this rate had taken the lowest value among all the member states of the European Union. The average yearly rate of acceptance of asylum applications for the period 2011-2019 reached slightly over 23%.

Table 2. Applications for international protection and positive decisions concerning granting an asylum and granting subsidiary protection, 2011-2019.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 a, b, c).

Year	Number of applications for international protection ⁷	Decisions of asylum granting	Decisions of subsidiary protection granting
2011	756	108	261
2012	753	49	149
2013	707	95	256
2014	1 156	82	295
2015	1 525	71	399
2016	1 478	148	302
2017	1 451	29	118
2018	1 701	47	118
2019	1 922	61	86
Total	11 449	690	1984

In 2019, the most recent year included in this analysis, 1922 applications for international protection have been filed in the Czech Republic, and the applicants were Armenians (over 19% of all applicants), Ukrainians (over 16%) and Georgians (less than 12%).

⁷ The year refers to the date when the processing of the application commenced.

Table 3. Applications for international protection and positive decisions of granting an asylum and granting subsidiary protection by citizenship of the applicant or grantee (top 10 countries by number of applicants), 2019.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 a, b, c).

Country	Number of applications for international protection (2019)	Positive decisions of asylum granting (2019)	Decisions of subsidiary protection granting (2019)
Armenia	372	0	0
Ukraine	311	3	10
Georgia	224	0	0
Vietnam	143	0	0
Kazachstan	109	1	1
Russia	90	26	1
Uzbekistan	85	1	1
Moldova	43	0	0
Syria	40	0	22
Venezuela	33	0	<i>no data</i>

Finally, speaking about the positive decisions of granting international protection, the most frequent nationality of the asylum grantee in Czechia for a period of 2004-2019 has been Russian, followed by Belarussian, Ukrainian, Burmese and Iraqi. The highest number of positive decisions of granting a subsidiary protection (period 2006-2019) has been witnessed by the Ukrainians, followed by Belarussians, Iraqi, the stateless persons and Kazakhs. It needs to be pointed out, however, that the analysed numbers are so small, that such ranking statistically makes little sense and is presented here only for informative purposes.

Table 4: Positive decisions of asylum granting by citizenship of the grantee (top 10 countries for 2004 - 2019 period).

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 b).

Country	Decisions of asylum granting (2004 - 2019)
Russian Federation	309
Belarus	241
Ukraine	180
Myanmar	178
Iraq	160
Kazakhstan	97
Armenia	75
Stateless	62
Syrian Arab Republic	60
Uzbekistan	60

Table 5: Positive decisions of subsidiary protection granting by citizenship of the grantee (top 10 countries for 2006 - 2019 period).

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 c).

Country	Decisions of subsidiary protection granting (2006 - 2019)
Ukraine	402
Belarus	261
Iraq	217
Stateless	189
Kazakhstan	140
Russia	91
Afghanistan	63
China	12
Armenia	12
Vietnam	10

Table 6: Positive decisions of asylum granting by citizenship of the grantee (top 10 countries in 2019).
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 b).

Country	Decisions of asylum granting (2019)
Russian Federation	26
Turkey	4
Kyrgyzstan	4
Cuba	4
Egypt	4
Ukraine	3
Azerbaijan	2
Kazakhstan	2
Myanmar	2
Somalia	2

Table 7: Positive decisions of subsidiary protection granting by citizenship of the grantee (top 10 countries for 2019).
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 c).

Country	Decisions of granting of subsidiary protection (2019)
Syria	22
Libya	11
Ukraine	10
Stateless	9
China	8
Yemen	7
Belarus	3
Kyrgyzstan	3
Saudi Arabia	3
Somalia	3

Picture: Jean Carlo Emer/Unsplash.com

(in the report document it was called chapter 5.2)

? 6.6 Abel & Cohen's Dataset – comparison with the local data

Finally, as mentioned in the introductory part of the report one of its aims is also to compare the available statistics with estimations of bilateral international migration flows proposed by Abel and Cohen (2019). The latest dataset analysed by the authors came from the United Nations Population Division (UNCPD) and covers the 5-year period between 2011 and 2015. According to their estimates, almost 42 thousand people immigrated to Slovakia within this period of time. The most numerous groups of migrants came from Czechia, Hungary, Ukraine, Romania and Poland (see table 14).

Table 8: Abel and Cohen's estimations of the number of immigrants to Czechia between 2011-2015.
Source: Abel & Cohen 2019.

Country	Number of immigrants to Czechia between 2011 - 2015
Ukraine	35 709
Slovakia	20 024
Vietnam	15 169
Russia	8 183
Poland	5 294
Germany	3 178
Moldova	2 814
Bulgaria	1 758
Montenegro	1 498
Kazachstan	1 331
Other	19 633
Total	114 591

Figure 15 & Figure 5 are identical?

Figure 15. Changes in size of biggest national groups among immigrants in Czechia between September 2011 and September 2020.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

Similar conclusion one may draw from analysing changes in the distribution of nationalities in the overall number of migrants living in the Czech Republic over the last ten years. Among six largest immigrant groups present in Czechia, only the Slovaks insignificantly increased their share in an overall group of foreign residents in the country. As one may see in Chart 16 below, the relative declines of the shares of Ukrainians, Vietnamese, Russians, Poles and Germans in the overall migrants' group (between September 2011 and 2020) oscillated between less than 1% and slightly over 3%. At the same time, the relative share of nationalities other than the aforementioned rose by almost 7%, which proves that the national diversity in a group of immigrants in Czechia is increasing.

Figure 16. Changes in the distribution of nationalities in the overall group of immigrants in Czechia, September 2011 to September 2020.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

As it has already been said, the biggest group of immigrants living in Czechia are the Ukrainian nationals. The growing presence of Ukrainian nationals in Czechia is linked with the economic situation in Ukraine as well as with geographical, cultural and historical proximity between the countries. Also the Russian annexation of the Crimea and a partially successful attempt to invade and occupy East Ukraine substantially impacted the immigration patterns of Ukrainian to Czechia (as well as other countries of the V4 region) in the last decade.

Figure 17. Change in the number of Ukrainians and Slovaks in Czechia between June 2010 and June 2021.
Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 f).

As pointed out by many migration scholars focusing on Central and Eastern Europe, the war and uncertainty of the political situation in Ukraine have been important push factors for many young Ukrainians who left the country over the last decade (Leontiyeva & Kopecká 2018: 8). On the other hand, Zdeněk Uherek sheds a different light on this issue, pointing to the changes in the structure of types of residence documents held by the Ukrainian nationals in the Czech Republic. The Czech scholar stresses, that while, according to him, the war in Ukraine had not itself caused the number of Ukrainian migrants to rise, it might have had, to some extent, shifted the patterns of applications for residence permits in the group of Ukrainians.

Picture: [Maxime Vandenberg/Unsplash.com](https://unsplash.com/photos/MaximeVandenberg)

7. Migration narrative scenario

Demographic patterns in Czechia

In this subchapter we focus on migration potential of Czechia as a sending and a host country, taking into account the important push and pull factors such as the demographic structure, national economy, development of technology, social attitudes towards foreigners, governance indicators and ecological factors. As such, these scenario narratives do not aim to foresee the migration future of the Czech Republic but rather outline the possible directions in which demographic processes can develop, also with regard to international migration.

The Czech society is ageing. Nearly twenty percent of the population is currently above 65 years old (Eurostat, 2021 a). Meanwhile, the share of the working age population since has been shrinking since 2007 and in 2020 amounted to 63% of the overall population (OECD, 2021 c). The life expectancy at birth in Czechia is 78 years old on average - 75 for males and 81 for females (Eurostat, 2021 b). The total fertility rate in the Czech Republic, in 2019 amounting to 1.71, became the third higher in the EU27, ex aequo with Ireland (Eurostat, 2021 c).

According to the 2018 population forecast produced at the Faculty of Sciences of Charles University in Prague, until 2050 the rates of mortality and fertility will rise by 7 and 3 percentage points at the maximum, respectively. Moreover, it is very probable for migration inflows to Czechia to increase and in thirty years achieve the level of 40 thousand migrants arriving in the country annually (Bleha et al., 2018: 221). Based on the population projections, we may conclude that in the following thirty years Czechia will not be in a high risk of a significant depopulation.

When it comes to the economic indicators, Czechia has one of the lowest unemployment rates among the OECD countries. For the age group 25 to 75 years old unemployment equated merely to 2.4% in 2021 (OECD, 2021 d). The structure of GDP, and hiring by sector, indicate that the Czech economy should be seen as developed one. In 2020, the industry constituted 33% of the annual gross domestic product in Czechia, agriculture - 2%, and services - 65% (WorldBank, 2021 a). In 2019 the industry hired 37% of the working age population, agriculture – 2.6% and services – 60.4% (WorldBank, 2021 b). Taking into account the relatively high employment rates for the industry and services sectors, we may conclude that these sectors can be potential sources of employment for migrants.

The next important factor to discuss is technological development and its impact on migration. Czechia is responding to the global technological process. In 2020, expenditures for research and development equated there to 1.9% of the annual GDP which placed the country slightly below the EU average (2.4%). This score is the second-highest among the Central European countries, after Slovenia (OECD 2021 e). The progressing technological development may have a great impact on the Czech industry, which we identified as a potential source of employment for migrants.

Needless to say, the political situation impacts immigrants living conditions in the country as well. In the latest parliamentary election in October 2021, the centre-right electoral coalition of Spolu won with the result of 27% of votes (Gniazdowski & Wasiuta 2021). The newly elected government with Petr Fiala as the PM expressed the will of focusing on strengthening democracy and promotion of human rights. At the same time, according to the declared agenda, Spolu is not in favour of the reception system based on quota on immigration. Instead, the party stands for limiting irregular migration (Dębiec & Wasiuta, 2021). Therefore, we may conclude that in the following years Czechia will likely not become a popular country for those seeking asylum and the situation of asylum seekers and refugees will not improve.

Another important factor to discuss are social attitudes toward migrants and refugees. As a study conducted in 2017 by the think-tank Glopolis revealed, Czech public opinion is rather unfavourable towards those groups. The respondent's narratives indicated that migrants and refugees are: *'threat to a civilization, hidden terrorists, unadaptable and unthankful'* (Brožová et al., 2018: 9). As the study also revealed the fear from newcomers in the society on a deeper level stems from the perception of the state institutions and ruling elites as incompetent and alienated, therefore the capacities of Czech Republic to help refugees and even some citizens as limited (Ibidem).

According to Brožová, Jurečková and Pacovská, media and politicians played an important role in building negative narrative about migrants in Czechia. For instance, as they point out:

[A]ccording to a study conducted by MEDIAN for People in Need, for 84 % of Czechs the TV is the main source of information about migration. 39 % use mainly the internet, (...) A team of researchers from the Masaryk-university in Brno analysed and compared the two main evening news programs by the two biggest TV channels: Události by the public broadcaster Czech TV and Televizní noviny by the biggest commercial channel Nova. Both programs have shown the same tendencies: presenting refugees as an issue of administration, police activities and a threat, or as victims and people in need (less often), but almost never as individuals with their own stories and motives' (Ibidem).

Finally, we need to consider the environment as a driver for migrations in the future. Czechia is located in the temperate zone. According to the World Bank, in the next three decades the country will be at a relatively low risk of drastic increase in temperatures, decrease in precipitation and of frequent occurrence of extreme weather events (WorldBank, 2021 c), which means that the climate changes in Czechia are projected as mild. According to the climate projections prepared by the World Bank, until 2050 the annual mean temperature in Czechia will increase by ca. 1 Celsius degree. During the same period, the precipitation is expected to decrease which will result in droughts in the summer months and the heavy rains following it - hence sudden storms and floods are expected to occur. In the light of these words, the Czech Republic will not be a source of climate emigration, since the results of the climate changes witnessed in Central Europe are not likely to affect the region to the extent, where it would be impossible to live there. However, importantly, Czechia might become a destination for the climate refugees.

Migration prospects

The number of foreigners in Czechia has been steadily rising over the last decade. In 2010 their number equated to nearly 425 thousand, while in 2020 – there were over 630 thousand foreigners residing in the country (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). The biggest share of foreigners reside in Czechia on a basis of a permanent residence permits (nearly a half of all immigrants). Around one quarter of migrants living in Czechia consists of the EU nationals granted temporary residence permits. Another quarter consists of migrants granted long-term residence permits and long-term visas. The data for 2020 concerning residence permits' held by foreigners in the Czech Republic is presented in the chart below:

Figure 18. Foreigners in Czech Republic in 2020 by the type of residence, (N=632 570)

Source: Czech Statistical Office (2021 k).

As has already been pointed out, the number of migrants living in Czechia increases. According to the data provided by the Czech Foreign Police, in December 2020 there were ca. 650 thousand third-country nationals living in the territory of Czechia, including grantees of international protection (Ministry of Interior of the Czech Republic, 2020 b). The high share of permanent residence permits granted suggests that most probably a significant proportion of migrants will settle in Czechia. With regards to spatial distribution of migrants in the country Brožová, Jurečková and Pacovská point out that:

'The highest concentration of foreigners is typically in the capital – over 184,000 foreigners live in Prague, followed by Central Bohemia with 65,000, the South-West with 47,000 and the North-West with 52,000. The lowest concentration of foreigners is typically in the Moravian region (26,000). The population density corresponds with the unemployment rate in the particular regions of the Czech Republic. In 2015, the lowest unemployment rate was in Prague (3%), the highest in the Moravian Silesian region (7.6%)' (Brožová et al., 2018: 2).

Due to the history of communist rule in Czechia, migration networks in the country consist mostly of relatively young migrants. Most of the immigrants belong to the first migrant generation. The six largest migrant groups of the EU nationals living in Czechia are: Slovaks, Germans, Polish, Romanians, Bulgarians and Hungarians.

The major national group of foreign residents of Czechia is composed of Slovaks, whose number is steadily growing year to year. For instance, the number of Slovak citizens holding valid residence permits in 2010 amounted to over 70 thousand, in 2015 there were as many 100 thousand of them, and in 2020 – 124 thousand (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). Migrants from the Slovak Republic are located not only in Prague, the capital city of Czechia, but also in central and southern parts of the country, namely in Střední Čechy, Plzeňský kraj, Severovýchod and Jihovýchod regions (Ibidem). Taking into account the trends witnessed over the last decade, we may conclude that the positive trend in Slovaks migration to Czechia will be maintained, due to geographical, cultural and historical proximity between the Slovak and Czech nations.

Due to the history of communist rule in Czechia, migration networks in the country consist mostly of relatively young migrants. Most of the immigrants belong to the first migrant generation. The six largest migrant groups of the EU nationals living in Czechia are: Slovaks, Germans, Polish, Romanians, Bulgarians and Hungarians.

The second largest group of foreigners living in the Czech Republic are Germans, whose number since 2015 remained at the level of around 20 thousand persons. German citizens are located mostly in big cities like Prague, Brno, Karlovy Vary and Teplice, and they are employed in big companies, which suggest that they hold high professional and/or educational qualifications. In 2020 more than three quarters of Germans living in Czechia were males with temporary stay permits (Ministry of Interior of the Czech Republic 2021 b). We may assume that this particular migration flow consists mostly of persons undertaking professional activities in Czechia and its volume in the following decades may remain the same or slightly increase, if the economic situation of Czechia will further improve.

The next biggest group comprises of Polish citizens, whose number slightly rising during the last decade. In 2010, in Czechia there were 18 thousand Poles registered, in 2015 – 19 thousand, and in 2020 – 20 thousand. Poles are dispersed across the territory of the country, and the locations where many of them live are the cities such as, e.g., Prague, Karviná, Mladá Boleslav. In 2020 half of the Polish immigrants were holding temporary and half were holding permanent residence permits. Interestingly, when it comes to the temporary stay, males outbalanced females twice (6 thousand: 3 thousand), while for a group residing in the country on a basis of permanent residence permits a high feminisation rate has been witnessed according to the official statistics. Namely, in 2020, 7 thousand Polish females were granted a permanent stay permits, while only 3 thousand Polish males were holding such documents at that time (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). We can assume that in the three following decades the number of Poles will slightly but steadily increase, especially because of the high feminisation rate in the group.

Another two numerous national groups among foreigners residing in Czechia are Romanians and Bulgarians whose numbers in 2020 equated to around 18 thousand. Both groups are located mainly in the capital city and are characterised by the high share of temporary stay permits. Consequently, we may conclude that the size of both groups is likely to remain on the same level or perhaps slightly increase in the following thirty years, due to the high share of temporary stay permits' holders among Romanians and Bulgarians, as well as due to the possible long-term impact of pandemic on economic situation of Romania and Bulgaria.

In 2020, the third-country citizens constituted 63% of all migrants living in Czechia (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). The largest groups we will take into account are: Ukrainians, Vietnamese, Russians, Mongolians, Chinese, US citizens, Indians and Serbs. Ukrainians in Czechia constitute the largest migrant group of non-EU origin. In 2010, 124 thousand Ukrainians had been registered in the Czech Republic. This number, according to the official statistics, decreased slightly, to reach 105 thousand in 2015. However, in 2020, in spite of the impact of COVID-19 pandemic, 165 thousand Ukrainians were known to be registered in the country (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). Consequently, a trend of the increasing number of Ukrainians in Czechia can be identified, regardless of a temporary decrease witnessed around 2015. Importantly, in 2020, more than a half of Ukrainians were granted a permanent stay permission in the country.

Ukrainians living in the Czech Republic are located not only in the capital city, but also in northern and western parts of the country (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 a). An important characteristic of the Ukrainians' group is its high feminisation rate. In 2020, 38% of Ukrainian females in Czechia were holding temporary stay permits and 48% - a permanent ones (MI 2020 b). Besides, it can be mentioned that in an insignificant number of Ukrainians in the Czech Republic are grantees of some form of international protection. Since 2010, 90 Ukrainians have received a refugee status (Czech Statistical Office 2021 b) and 397 – subsidiary protection (Czech Statistical Office 2021 c). Although there are some refugees in the country who hold Ukrainian citizenship, the influx of Ukrainians has its origin in the economic factors, and the rejection rate for applications for international protections is very high. For instance, in 2014 it totalled to 95% compared to 99% in 2019 (Czech Statistical Office 2021 a). Taking into account the data from the last ten years, the military conflict in Ukraine and a cultural and linguistic proximity between both nations, we may presume that the number of Ukrainians in Czechia will increase in the following three decades.

The second-largest group of the third-country citizens consists of Vietnamese, whose number over the last decade has been remaining steadily at the level of ca. 60 thousand people (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). The Vietnamese live across all the country, including the Moravs region (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 a). A high share of permanent stay permit holders is witnessed in this group. In 2020, 84% of all Vietnamese were allowed permanent stay in Czechia, which indicates the high probability of their extended stay in the country. The feminisation rate among temporary and permanent stay recipients equated in 2020 to 46% (Czech Statistical Office 2021 k). Considering the factors above, we may assume that the size of the group will remain stable with potential to further grow.

The next biggest migrant group among the third country nationals are Russian citizens whose number has been steadily growing over the last ten years. In 2010, the number of Russians living in Czechia had equated to 31 thousand, while five years later it was known to have reached 35 thousand. In 2020, the number of Russian citizens amounted to 41 thousand, including over 19 thousand holders of permanent stay permit (Czech Statistical Office 2021 k). It is worth mentioning that in the Russians' group females outbalance males - in 2020 the feminisation ratio amounted to 55% (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). Russians in Czechia are living mostly in Prague, but also in Ostrava, Nymburk, Liberec and Karlovy Vary (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 a). Taking into account the tendency of growth in the size of the group, a high feminisation rate and a large number of permanent stay permit holders, we might predict that the Russian network is prone to increase in size in the following years.

Subsequently, Mongolians are also one of the rapidly growing migrant groups in Czechia. In 2015, their number equated to nearly 6 thousand whilst in 2020, there were as many as over 10 thousand of them living in Czechia (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). Interestingly, Mongolians are not located mostly in the capital city, which is a frequent pattern of settlement for international immigrants. The biggest group of Mongolians in the Czech Republic lives in Česká Lípa. The next-largest groups of Mongolians are located in the cities of Pardubice and Mladá Boleslav (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 a). Also, the permanent stay holders rate is relatively high as in 2020 equated to 52% of all Mongolians in Czechia (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). Taking into account the growth of the group size, the number of Mongolian permanent residence permit holders and potential destination cities spread all over the country it might be assumed that the number of Mongolians will steadily increase in Czechia during the following three decades.

The Chinese living in Czechia also witnessed a growth in number over the last years. The increase of Chinese in Czechia had been steady (around 5 thousand persons annually) until the recent, significant influx in 2020, when nearly 8 thousand Chinese people were registered in the country (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). The second group with such a big recent growth in size consists of Serbs, whose number had been oscillating between approximately 2000 and 2500 until 2015, whilst in 2020 it reached nearly 6 thousand. In Czechia, Serbs and Chinese live mostly in Prague. Another common trait of those two groups are relatively high feminisation rates, which in 2020 equated to 30% in the Serbian group and 47% among Chinese (Czech Statistical Office, 2021 k). We may presume that the sizes of both groups will be increasing during the next thirty years due to a vast growth in the size of both of them, especially in case of the Chinese migrants.

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